

A 128-channel neural stimulation and recording ASIC for scalable cortical visual prosthesis

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Abstract—Blindness affects millions of people around the world, being triggered by various defects within the human visual system. Different kinds of prostheses have been developed, which can stimulate the retina, the optical nerve or even the visual cortex, creating a basic form of vision. Here, we present a scalable ASIC and data-acquisition system that enables neural stimulation and recording in the visual cortex. The ASIC includes 128 area-efficient fully-programmable stimulators and 64 low-noise artifact-tolerant recording channels. The chip has been implemented in a 55nm CMOS technology, and our measurement results demonstrate its ability to stimulate and record simultaneously from the same electrode or from neighboring electrodes, which is important to enable the implementation of visual cortex prostheses.

Keywords—visual prosthesis, neural stimulation, neural recording, cortical, CMOS

I. INTRODUCTION

Vision is one of the most important senses we have, and still loss of sight affects millions of people around the world. Damages to the eye and top layers of the retina may be alleviated by using retinal prostheses [1]–[4], which stimulate the retina to create a perception of vision [5], [6]. Recent retinal implants are capable of high-resolution stimulation by using application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs) which implement simple current stimulation and shared charge-balancing functionality [2]–[4]. Those devices can achieve small channel area and low power consumption while providing optical data input or wireless power transfer [2]–[4]. However, when the retina or the visual nerve are damaged, there is a need to create the perception of vision by directly stimulating the visual cortex [5]–[8]. To create a sufficiently high-quality image while stimulating the visual cortex, high-density cortical neural probes must be implanted and coupled with high-channel-count stimulation electronics. As cortical stimulators are in direct contact with brain tissue, they require more accurate current-delivery, charge-balancing and safety-monitoring circuits [9], which translate to higher circuit complexity, larger area and more stringent power constraints to prevent tissue heating. Due to the larger size and 3-dimensional shape of the visual cortex, current cortical visual prosthetics either cannot provide the required number of stimulation channels [5], [10] or rely on large, external equipment to drive a high number of implanted electrodes [8], or both [5], [7].

An envisioned visual prosthesis system is shown in Fig. 1. Here, the captured reality is processed into simplified image representations, which are fed to one or more stimulators by means of stimulation pattern commands. The current pulses produced by the stimulators will create perceptions of light in

Fig. 1. Components and operation of a cortical visual prosthesis.

the visual field called phosphenes, whose locations within the visual field are related to the physical location of the electrodes [5]. Because the image to be created in the brain can be arbitrary, an important requirement for the stimulator is to be able to stimulate any possible combination and amount of electrodes simultaneously within the implanted electrode array. However, considering that phosphene vision does not require different stimulation patterns for each electrode [11], multiple electrodes can be stimulated with the same current pattern. To calibrate the stimulation parameters and monitor the implant’s functionality, the stimulator requires readout circuits that can record neural data during and in-between stimulation pulses, while being able to reject large artefacts.

To tackle the above-mentioned limitations and system requirements, in this work we present a small-area neural stimulation and recording ASIC (RWIC) to enable cortical visual prostheses that can be scaled to thousands of stimulation channels. The proposed RWIC is meant to be directly bonded to a passive, polyamide-based flexible probe which is implanted in the visual cortex. This paper is organized as follows: the RWIC architecture is introduced in Section II, the block-level implementation is detailed in Section III, the chip manufacturing and developed acquisition system are explained in Section IV, while the measurement results are presented in Section V.

II. RWIC ARCHITECTURE

The proposed RWIC architecture is shown in Fig. 2 and consists of the following main blocks: 64 recording channels (CH), 128 output stages (OS), 8 stimulator units (SU) and a digital controller. This chip supports the connection to 128 electrodes, which can all be stimulated simultaneously. Recording can be performed in a subset of 64 electrodes, which is programmable. The stimulation is carried out with fully customizable, constant-current rectangular pulses, whereby the amplitude and duration of each pulse are adjustable independently for each SU. Our proposed stimulation functionality is split into two parts: an OS and a

Fig. 2. Architecture of the proposed RWIC showing the main sub-blocks: 8 stimulation units, 128 output stages and 64 recording channels.

SU. There is an OS for each electrode, which consist of high-voltage (HV), voltage-to-current converters. The OSs are driven by the SUs, each one composed of a timing generator, an IDAC and a current-to-voltage converter. In this proposed configuration, a single SU can drive multiple OSs. Therefore, multiple electrodes can be simultaneously stimulated with the same current waveform. This enables the scaling of the stimulation functionality to a high number of electrodes without the need for a complete SU for each electrode.

The 64 channels can record neural activity either during stimulation (from non-stimulated electrodes) or in between stimulation pulses (from stimulated electrodes). Each channel consists of two electrode-selection switch matrixes, an instrumentation amplifier (IA), an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) driver, an impedance-measurement signal generator, and an automatic recovery reset. The IA uses a fully differential AC-coupled architecture with variable gain to remove the DC offset and optimize the dynamic range. Sixteen channels are time-multiplexed into a single ADC.

The digital controller of the ASIC is responsible for serializing the ADC data into a serial stream and exchanging configuration data through a high-speed SPI bus, for both the stimulator units and rest of the configuration registers. In addition, it generates all the required internal clocks, control signals and timings for the SU, OS, and CH.

III. BLOCK-LEVEL IMPLEMENTATION

A. Neural stimulation circuits

The stimulation circuits in the RWIC can generate square current pulses of programmable settings: amplitude, duration, frequency, polarity (anodic or cathodic first) and number of periods. A typical cathodic-first stimulation waveform is shown in Fig. 3. Because of the provided flexible programmability, the stimulators can generate biphasic or monophasic, bipolar or monopolar pulses. Each stimulation pulse is followed by a passive charge-balancing phase, which prevents electrode damage by ensuring a net zero charge flow.

The stimulation current reference is generated by a 7-bit current digital-to-analog converter (IDAC) with a $1\mu\text{A}$ least significant bit (LSB), and a 0-127 μA output current. The IDAC has a PMOS output stage and is partitioned in a 4-bit thermometer section and a 3-bit binary section to co-optimize the area of the digital decoding circuitry and the unit-current source.

Fig. 3 Top: schematics of the stimulation circuits including the shared SUs and individual OSs for each electrode. Bottom: SU output waveform and programmable parameters.

Each OS drives one dedicated electrode and can connect to any of the 8 SUs through a switch matrix. Multiple OSs can connect to a single SU. Therefore, at one given time, any number of electrodes can be stimulated, but there can be at most 8 different stimulation patterns. The electrode driver consists of a constant current push-pull stage, with each half consisting of a current-reference transistor and a cascode. The cathodic current (between the electrode and ground) is generated with a low-voltage current-mirror transistor and a HV cascode transistor. The anodic current (between the 6V stimulation supply and electrode) is generated with a HV current mirror and a HV cascode. A switch disconnects the output driver from the electrode when stimulation is not active. After each stimulation pulse, the electrode is discharged through a resistor to the mid-supply reference, thus forming the passive charge-balancing phase.

B. Neural signal recording circuits

The recording circuit schematic is detailed in Fig. 4. The small neural signals (μV to mV range) are amplified, low-pass filtered, time-multiplexed (16:1) and digitized by a 12-bit capacitive successive-approximation-register (SAR) ADC running at 320kSps. The AC-coupled IA features three gain selections (12/25/50) to maximize the ADC dynamic range and reduce the input referred noise. The IA employs PMOS based pseudo-resistors (R_p) and feedback capacitors (C_2) to establish a high-pass corner frequency of less than 1Hz. The operation transconductance amplifier (OTA) is implemented with a folded cascode architecture and capacitive common-mode feedback. To reduce the common-mode noise and improve the quality of the recording, 9 reference possibilities are provided: one large body electrode which is used as return path during stimulation, and 8 small electrodes which can be connected together to form a low-impedance reference. The recording channel includes additional switches and logic to enable “blinking” during simultaneous stimulation in the same electrode. Thus, the channel input gets automatically disconnected from the electrode when the stimulator is enabled. This prevents large stimulation artefacts at the input of the IA.

Fig. 4. Recording channel schematic showing the neural amplifier, auto-recovery circuit and auxiliary components.

Since fast recovery from saturation (e.g. due to large stimulation artifacts) is crucial for this application, an automatic recovery circuit is proposed in this work. This circuit is composed of a pair of window comparators, which resets the channel when the outputs are close to saturation. This reset is applied through two switches placed in parallel with the pseudo-resistors. Thus, a quick channel recovery of $<1\text{ms}$ can be achieved, even when a large amplitude signal was present at the input.

Two additional features have been included in the channels to guarantee safe stimulation: i) a low gain setting (0.16V/V) implemented with an attenuator, which allows to monitor the stimulation voltage formed at the electrode interface; and ii) an electrode-impedance monitoring circuit consisting of a programmable square-wave current generator (1/10/100 nA, 10-2000 Hz) which injects current pulses into the electrode. The voltage formed at the electrode is readout by the channel and used to calculate the impedance.

IV. MANUFACTURING AND ACQUISITION SYSTEM

The ASIC was manufactured in a 55-nm CMOS HV technology and its microphotograph is shown in Fig. 5. The right side of the ASIC contains two groups of 64 pads to which the passive probes are directly bonded [12]. The OSs are placed underneath each bonding pad and their layout matches the pad pitch ($150 \times 150 \mu\text{m}^2$). The left side of the ASIC contains the 64 recording channels, 8 stimulation units, digital core and common circuits such as biasing and testing. The dimensions of the ASIC are $3.9 \times 4.1 \text{mm}^2$. The total stimulation-circuit area per electrode is 0.024mm^2 , including the individual OS and shared SUs. Thus, it is possible to scale the stimulation capabilities with just $150 \times 150 \mu\text{m}^2$ per extra electrode. The total recording channel area is 0.043mm^2 .

To evaluate and demonstrate the functionality of the RWIC and enable future *in vivo* experiments, a complete acquisition system is developed (Fig. 5). It consists of a control box and a headstage. The control box contains an FPGA and memory buffer, galvanically-isolated power supply for the RWIC and general purpose IOs. It can connect to a computer via a USB 3.0 interface or to the pattern generator system via a SPI interface, while handling recording and stimulation of up to 4096 electrodes. The RWICs are bonded on stackable printed circuit boards (PCBs) which form a small and light-weight headstage compatible with small rodents.

Fig. 5. RWIC microphotograph and picture of the complete data-acquisition system: control box and a small, light-weight stack headstage.

V. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

A. Recording functionality

The RWIC has been bonded on a test PCB to characterize

Fig. 6. Top: measured recording channel frequency response and input referred noise. Bottom: 4-channel saline recording using a passive neural probe with TiN electrodes. A pre-recorded neural signal is applied to the saline solution and recorded with the RWIC.

the electrical performance of the proposed RWIC, a test setup consisting of the RWIC on a test PCB, PC to SPI bridge, logic analyzer and spectrum analyzer are used. The transfer function and input-referred-noise spectrum of the recording channel are measured with a spectrum analyzer (from an analog output) and shown in Fig. 6 (top). The mid-band gains are 50.4, 25.6 and 14.8V/V, and the bandwidth is from 0.75Hz to 7.1kHz (at the highest gain). The input referred noise is $6.1 \mu\text{Vrms}$ within the action-potential signal band (300Hz to 5kHz) and $7.3 \mu\text{Vrms}$ in the local-field-potential band (5Hz to 1kHz). To demonstrate the ability to record neural signals, a saline-solution experiment has been performed by connecting the RWIC to a passive neural probe with $12 \times 12 \mu\text{m}^2$ TiN electrodes ($Z \approx 150 \text{k}\Omega$). The probe is submerged in the saline solution where a pre-recorded neural signal is applied, and the digital output of the RWIC is captured by a logic analyzer and shown in Fig. 6 (bottom).

Fig. 7. Measured simultaneous stimulation and recording waveforms. Top: when recording and stimulating the same electrode, the *Blank* switch is opened to avoid large artifacts at the input of the channel. Bottom: when recording and stimulating different electrodes, the *Blank* switch is kept closed and the automatic recovery circuit is triggered every time a saturation event is detected.

B. Simultaneous recording and stimulation

The simultaneous stimulation and recording capabilities of the RWIC are demonstrated in Fig. 7. Fig. 7 (top) shows measured $1.5V_{pp}$ stimulation pulses with a superimposed $10mV_{pp}$, $2kHz$ sinewave signal mimicking the low-amplitude neural signals, when recording and stimulation are performed on the same electrode (*EL 1*). The channel output is not affected by the large amplitude stimulation pulses because the *Blank* switch is open during the event. Since the stimulation pulse is charge balanced, the channel can immediately continue recording the low-amplitude signal.

When we record (*EL 1*) and stimulate (*EL 2*) from neighboring electrodes, the channel will pick up large stimulation artifacts because the *Blank* switch remains closed during the stimulation event (Fig. 7 bottom). To be able to capture the neural data, instead of global blanking, the RWIC includes an automatic recovery circuit in each channel. This way, the channel can recover instantly after the large artifact ($0.8V_{pp}$ in our measurement) and resumes recording.

C. Comparison with the state of the art

The RWIC are available in Table I. Compared to the generic neural stimulator [9] and previous cortical stimulators [7], the proposed architecture of the RWIC achieves smaller area per stimulation channel and higher number of simultaneous stimulation channels, which makes it scalable to high electrode count visual prosthesis with compact size. In addition, the presence of recording channels allows for the continuous closed loop calibration of implant by recording the neural data from the neighboring neurons or the stimulated electrode potential. The recording function is supported by the active recovery circuits which allow the recording of neural signals with a fast recovery in the presence of large artefacts from the stimulator. In addition, the health of the electrodes can be monitored by using the electrode impedance measurement function.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates a scalable ASIC and data-acquisition system for simultaneous stimulation and recording

TABLE I. COMPARISON WITH STATE OF THE ART STIMULATION ASICS

	This work	ESSCIRC'22 [9]	ISSCC'20 [2]	IOP'19 [7]
Type	Cortical stimulator	Generic	Retinal	Cortical stimulator
No of channels Stim/Rec	128 / 64	32 / 32	1225 / 0	43 / 0
Stim. Supply [V]	+/- 3	+/-9	+/- 1.6	10
Max stim. Current [A]	127µ	10m	1m	111µ
Stim. waveform	Program. square	Arbitrary	Square	Program. square
Area/stim. ch [mm ²]	0.024	0.4*	0.007	0.19*
Electrode impedance monitoring	Yes	Yes	No	No
Charge balancing	Passive, individual	Passive, individual	Global	Passive, individual
Recording power/channel [µW]	30 (inc. all blocks)	11.8 (inc. LNA only)	-	-
Input noise [µV _{rms}]	7.3/6.1 (LFP/AP)	3.8/3.3 (LFP/AP)	-	-
BW [Hz]	0.7 – 7100	0.2 – 7500	-	-
Area /rec. ch [mm ²]	0.043	**	-	-
Artefact tolerance	6 Vpp	mV***	N/A	N/A
Artefact recovery time	< 1 ms	< 10ms***	N/A	N/A

*Estimated **not specified, 0.4 mm² includes recording and stimulation ***Relies on passive discharge, no mitigation in the channel

of the visual cortex. It provides fully-flexible and charge-balanced stimulation for 128 electrodes, and low-noise artifact-tolerant recording of 64 electrodes. The ASIC architecture allows upscaling to a higher number of electrodes with minimal area overhead, while the supporting system is capable of handling thousands of channels.

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